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Article

Reflections of New Education Policy – An Innovative Perspective

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ABSTRACT

Education is the pillar for human development. The new education policy-2020 is the vision for future India by focusing on the flexibility and innovation as per the global standards. This Policy emphasizes on the development of the creative potential along with the development of critical thinking and problem solving – but also social, ethical, and emotional capacities and dispositions. It also aims to facilitate an inclusive, participatory and holistic approach, which takes into consideration field experiences; empirical research, stakeholder feedback, as well as lessons learned from best practices. There are different provision for the students opting for multidisciplinary subjects. Moreover, the foreign universities would be able to open their campuses in India. The world is undergoing rapid changes in the knowledge landscape. The growing emergence of epidemics and pandemics will also call for collaborative research in infectious disease management and development of vaccines and the resultant social issues heightens the need for multidisciplinary learning. This Policy proposes the revision and revamping of all aspects of the education structure, including its regulation and governance, to create a new system that is aligned with the aspirational goals of 21st century. In this perspective, the present paper highlights the innovation aspects of the policy.

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1. Introduction

Education is fundamental for achieving full human potential, developing an equitable and just society, and promoting national development. Providing universal access to quality education is the key to India's continued ascent, and leadership on the global stage in terms of economic growth, social justice and equality, scientific advancement, national integration, and cultural preservation. Universal high-quality education is the best way forward for developing and maximizing our country's rich talents and resources for the good of the individual, the society, the country, and the world. India will have the highest population of young people in the world over the next decade, and our ability to provide high-quality educational opportunities to them will determine the future of our country. Education Policy lays particular emphasis on the development of the creative potential of each individual. It is based on the principle that education must develop not only cognitive capacities - both the 'foundational capacities' of literacy and numeracy and 'higher-order' cognitive capacities, such as critical thinking and problem solving - but also social, ethical, and emotional capacities and dispositions.

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 introduced recently is set to change the face of education ecosystem in the coming time. In the coming time, we may also hope to see bright young adults with innovative approach towards work and life. The policy places a welcome emphasis on a holistic, learner-centred, flexible system that seeks to transform India into a vibrant knowledge society. It rightfully balances the rootedness and pride in India as well as acceptance of the best ideas and practices of learning from across the globe. Its vision is truly global and at the same time Indian.

One of the New Education Policy's loftier goals is to bring two crore out-of-school children into the mainstream and integration of vocational education. Reduction in the burdensome syllabus, focus on the environmental aspect, value and ethics based resources and fair access to education is crucial aspects of education that are well covered by NEP. In several ways, NEP is liberating to students. They will

be much more empowered and have the opportunity to choose the subjects they wish to learn.

Another welcome step is an attempt to make higher education focused and research-oriented by bringing in a single regulator to look after all institutions barring medical and law colleges. The policy gives a fillip to holistic education by envisioning the convergence of science and arts streams. NEP 2020's sharp focus on research, multidisciplinary approaches and use of technology as well as professional upgradation of teachers' competence has the potential to transform the education landscape.

2. Key Reflections of the New Education Policy

India is a large and diverse country with a cornucopia of languages, dialects and mother tongues. A number of developed countries in the world educate their children in mother tongues. When world leaders call on me, they prefer to speak in their mother tongues even though they are proficient in English. Great scholars prefer to write and speak in their mother tongues. There is a certain pride associated with speaking one's mother tongue and we must inculcate this sense of pride in our children.

This National Education Policy envisions an education system rooted in Indian ethos that contributes directly to transforming India, that is Bharat, sustainably into an equitable and vibrant knowledge society, by providing high-quality education to all, and thereby making India a global knowledge superpower. The Policy envisages that the curriculum and pedagogy of our institutions must develop among the students a deep sense of respect towards the Fundamental Duties and Constitutional values, bonding with one's country, and a conscious awareness of one's roles and responsibilities in a changing world. The vision of the Policy is to instill among the learners a deep-rooted pride in being Indian, not only in thought, but also in spirit, intellect, and deeds, as well as to develop knowledge, skills, values, and dispositions that support responsible commitment to human rights, sustainable development and living, and global well-being, thereby reflecting a truly global citizen.

The new National Education Policy (NEP 2020) unveiled by the Union government is being seen as the most ambitious reform initiated in recent times. It introduces sweeping changes in pedagogy, teaching methods, fee structures, evaluation, regulatory mechanism and openness to global universities. India has the world's largest population of about 500 million in the age bracket of 5-24 years. Further, be it the number of colleges and universities, or students enrolled in higher education, the numbers are just phenomenal.

Estimated at over \$100 billion, the sector is poised for exponential expansion. The country is already the second-largest market for e-learning and internet in the world. A New Education Policy aims to facilitate an inclusive, participatory and holistic approach, which takes into consideration field experiences, empirical research, stakeholder feedback, as well as lessons learned from best practices. It is a progressive shift towards a more scientific approach to education. The prescribed structure will help to cater the ability of the child – stages of cognitive development as well as social and physical awareness. If implemented in its true vision, the new structure can bring India at par with the leading countries of the world.

The main thrust of this policy regarding higher education is to end the fragmentation of higher education by transforming higher education institutions into large multidisciplinary universities, colleges, and HEI clusters/Knowledge Hubs, each of which will aim to have 3,000 or more students. This would help build vibrant communities of scholars and peers, break down harmful silos, enable students to become well-rounded across disciplines including artistic, creative, and analytic subjects as well as sports, develop active research communities across disciplines including cross-disciplinary research, and increase resource efficiency, both material and human, across higher education. Implementation will be guided by the following principles. First, implementation of the spirit and intent of the Policy will be the most critical matter. Second, it is important to implement the policy initiatives in a phased manner, as each policy point has several steps, each of which requires the previous step to be implemented successfully. Third, prioritization will be important in

ensuring optimal sequencing of policy points, and that the most critical and urgent actions are taken up first, thereby enabling a strong base. Fourth, comprehensiveness in implementation will be key; as this Policy is interconnected and holistic, only a full-fledged implementation, and not a piecemeal one, will ensure that the desired objectives are achieved. Fifth, since education is a concurrent subject, it will need careful planning, joint monitoring, and collaborative implementation between the Centre and States. Sixth, timely infusion of requisite resources - human, infrastructural, and financial - at the Central and State levels will be crucial for the satisfactory execution of the Policy.

Finally, careful analysis and review of the linkages between multiple parallel implementation steps will be necessary in order to ensure effective dovetailing of all initiatives. This will also include early investment in some of the specific actions (such as the setting up of early childhood care and education infrastructure) that will be imperative to ensuring a strong base and a smooth progression for all subsequent programmes and actions.

3. Conclusion

The New Education Policy (NEP) 2020 that will certainly be a landmark in the history of education in India, has been approved by the government after wide-ranging consultations with diverse groups of people. The policy is comprehensive, holistic, far-sighted and will play a great role in facilitating the future growth of the nation.

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